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Kazak Halkının Milli Oyunlarının Toplanması ve İncelenmesi
Қазақ Халқының Ұлттық Ойындарының Жиналуы мен
Зерттелуі
Collection and Study of National Games of the Kazakh People

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Kazak Halkının Milli Oyunlarının Toplanması ve İncelenmesi

Öz

Makale, Kazak halkının milli oyunlarının derlenmesi ve incelenmesine önemli katkılarda bulunan etnografik bilim adamlarının ve Rus Oryantalistlerin çalışmalarının bilimsel bir incelemesini sunmaktadır. 17. ve 18. yüzyıllarda Rusya topraklarından Kazak topraklarına gönderilen araştırmacıların Ulusal Oyunlar üzerine yaptıkları özgün çalışmaların küçük bir analizi yapılacak ve etnografik bilim adamları adım adım bilimsever okuyucuya tanıtılacaktır.

Bilimsel incelemede Kazak Milli Oyunlarını derinlemesine inceleyerek, toplayarak, gruplandırarak ve kitaplaştırarak yayınlarken millet kültürüne önemli katkılarda bulunan A. A. Divayev gibi bilim adamlarının çalışmaları üzerinde durulacaktır. Sovyet döneminde milli oyunlarımızı derleyip sistemleştiren, etnopedagoji ve spor müsabakaları alanına girmesine öncülük eden birçok bilim adamının çalışmaları ele alınacaktır. Makalede, bağımsızlık döneminin genç bilim adamlarının Kazak oyunları ile ilgili bilimsel çalışmaları ve eski oyunların adları üzerine yaptıkları araştırmalar ayrıntılı olarak ele alınmaktadır.

Makale ayrıca öğretmenler ve genç bilim adamları için bilimsel bilgiler sağlamakta, Kazak Ulusal Oyunlarının incelenmesinin tarihini, gruplandırılmasını, ders kitaplarına dahil edilme aşamalarını ve eğitim alanındaki uygulamalarını anlatmaktadır. Spor ve milli bilgiler, geleneksel eğlence türlerinin bilimsel birikimleri, etnografya tarihine atıflar, eski el yazmaları ile çalışılarak sağlanan tarihsel veriler sunulmaktadır.

I. I. Rychkov, P. Pallas, F. S. Efremov, P. Kondyrev, E. A. Alektorov, A. Divayev, I. G. Andreev, G. V. Plehanov, A. A. Pokrovsky, A. Vasiliev, M. Gavrilov, M. Gunner, A. Kunanbaev, M. Auezov, M. Zhumabaev, E. Sagindykov, M. Tanekeev, B. Totenaev, M. Balgymbaev, A. Burkitbaev, E. Muhiddinov, A. Kuralbekuly, A. Sakimbayuly, M. Shotaev gibi bilim adamlarımızın milli oyunlar üzerine yazdıkları bilimsel çalışma ve düşüncelerin küçük bir özeti verilir ve yeni görüşler ifade edilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Milli Oyunlar, Beden Eğitimi, Etnografya, Çocuk Oyunları, Gençlik Oyunları, Milli Sporlar, Spor Oyunları.

Қазақ Халқының Ұлттық Ойындарының Жиналуы Мен Зерттелуі

Аңдатпа.

Мақалада қазақ халқының ұлттық ойындарының жиналуы мен зерттелуіне айтарлықтай үлес қосқан этнограф ғалымдар мен орыс ориенталистерінің еңбектеріне ғылыми шолу жасалады. 17-18 ғасырларда қазақ жеріне Ресей аумағынан жіберілген зерттеуші ғалымдардың ұлттық ойындар жөнінде жазып кеткен түпнұсқа еңбектеріне шағын талдаулар жүргізіліп, ғылымсүйер оқырманға этнограф ғалымдар кезең-кезеңімен таныстырылады.

Қазақ ұлттық ойындарын терең зерттеп, жинақтап, топтастырып, кітап ретінде басып шығарып, ұлт мәдениетіне елеулі үлес қосқан Ә.А.Диваев сынды ғалымдардың еңбектеріне ерекше тоқталып, ғылыми талданады.

Кеңес дәуірінде ұлттық ойындарымызды жинақтап, жүйелеп, этнопеддагогика саласы мен спорттық жарыстарға енуіне мұрындық болған бірнеше ғалымдардың да еңбектері сөз болады. Тәуелсіздік кезеңіндегі жас ғалымдардың да қазақ ойындары жайлы жазған ғылыми жұмыстары мен көне ойын атауларына қатысты зерттеулері мақалада жан-жақты қамтылған.

Сондай-ақ мақалада педагогтар мен жас ғалымдарға арналған ғылыми ақпараттар беріліп, қазақ ұлттық ойындарының зерттелу тарихы, топтастырылуы, оқулықтарға енгізіліп, білім саласында қолданысқа түсу кезеңдері айтылады. Спорт пен ұлттық таным, дәстүрлі ойын-сауық түрлерінің ғылыми жинақталуы, этнография тарихына жасалған сілтемелер, көне қолжазбалармен жұмыс жасай отырып берілген тарихи деректер ұсынылады.

И.И.Рычков, П.Паллас, Ф.С.Ефремов, П.Кондырев, Е.А.Алекторов, Ә.Диваев, И.Г. Андреев, Г.В.Плеханов, А.А. Покровский, А.Васильев, М. Гаврилов, М.Гуннер, А.Құнанбаев, М.Әуезов, М.Жұмабаев, Е.Сағындықов, М.Тәнекеев, Б.Төтенаев, М.Балғымбаев, Ә.Бүркітбаев, Е.Мұхиддинов, А.Құралбекұлы, Ә.Сәкімбайұлы, М.Шотаев сынды ғалымдарымыздың ұлттық ойындар жөнінде жазған ғылыми еңбектері мен ой-толғамдарына кішігірім шолу жасалып, тың пікірлер айтылады.

Тірек сөздер: Ұлттық Ойындар, Дене Тәрбиесі, Этнография, Балалар Ойыны, Жастар Ойыны, Ұлттық Спорт, Спорттық Ойындар.

Collection and Study of National Games of the Kazakh People

Abstract

The article provides a scientific review of the works of ethnographic scientists and Russian Orientalists who have made a significant contribution to the collection and study of the national games of the Kazakh people. A small analysis of the original works of research scientists sent to the Kazakh land from the territory of Russia in the 17th-18th centuries on National Games will be made, and ethnographic scientists will be introduced to the science-loving reader step by step.

The scientific analysis will focus on the work of such scientists as A. A. Divayev, who made a significant contribution to the culture of the nation by deeply studying, collecting, grouping, publishing the Kazakh National Games as a book. In the Soviet era, the works of several scientists who collected and systematized our national games, pioneered their entry into the field of ethnopedagogy and sports competitions will be discussed. The article covers in detail the scientific works of young scientists of the period of independence about the Kazakh games and their research on the names of ancient games.

The article also provides scientific information for teachers and young scientists, talks about the history of the study of the Kazakh National Games, their grouping, the stages of inclusion in textbooks and implementation in the field of Education. Sports and national knowledge, scientific accumulation of traditional types of entertainment, references to the history of ethnography, historical data provided by working with ancient manuscripts are presented.

A small analysis of scientific works and reflections of our scientists on national games such as I. I. Rychkov, P. Pallas, F. S. Efremov, P. Kondyrev, E. A. Alektorov, A. Divayev, I. G. Andreev, G. V. Plekhanov, A. A. Pokrovsky, A. Vasiliev, M. Gavrilov, M. Gunner, Scientific works and works of such scientists such as Sh. Ualikhanov, Y. Altynsarin, A. Kunanbayev, M. Auezov, M. Zhumabayev, E. Sagyndykov, M. Tanekeev, B. Tyndaev, M. Balgimbayev, A. Burkitbayev, E. Mukhiddinov, A. Kuralbekuly, A. Sakimbaevich.

Keywords: National Games, Physical Culture, Ethnography, Children's Game, Youth Game, National Sport, Sports Games.

Introduction

Collecting and studying the Kazakh national games started in the second half of the 18th century. After the Dzungar invasion, research expeditions from Russia began coming to the Kazakh land to colonize the weakened Kazakh country. Those scientists-travelers researched and noted whole information about everyday life of the Kazakh people: terrain, nature, people and traditions, even children's games and deeply studied them, with paying attention to some details, finally sent them to an Emperor as a handwriting.

In the 18th century in newspapers as «Sunday Leisure» and so on, there were printed short stories and studies about various Kazakh national games, and animal hunting Researches were done on several groups such as "special scientific research", "military review", "records of prisoners". Among them, there were scientists who, in addition to Kazakh culture and oral literature, deeply studied the theme of the national games, collected and wrote it down, and published it as a book .They are: I.I. Rychkov, P. Pallas, F.S. Efremov, P. Kondyrev, E. A. Alektorov, A. Divaev, I. G. Andreev, G.V. Plekhanov, A.A. Pokrovsky. M. Gunner etc.

In the next period of research there were many scientists as M. Tanekeev, B. Totenaev, M. Balgimbaev, A. Burkitbaev, E. Muhiddinov who studied our national heritage in the Soviet era in connection with ethnopedagogy from a class point of view and tried to revive our original culture.

Description of materials and methods

So, one of the urgent problems of today is to raise the future generation in a way needed for modern world, so they follow a vigorous, healthy lifestyle, often go out into nature, play more in the fresh air, and are free from internet addiction. We should notice that children rarely or nearly never do beneficial things by themselves, so for the health of young generation mentors and teachers must educate them to be active playing our national games.

A healthy generation is the guarantee of a healthy nation and a strong country. It is obvious and undoubtedly that only those young people who have undergone comprehensive physical training from childhood through various national games will become the future of the country. Our national games are a set of interesting exercises that not only train our physical body, but also strengthen our intellectual abilities and develop our mental and quick decision-making abilities.

National games are a system of many exercises that not only teach the young generation to ride a horse, but also accustom them to acrobatics, harness, courage, marksmanship, accuracy, eloquence, thoroughness, thoughtfulness and intelligence. By making our national games a part of our daily life we raise brave and courageous Kazakhs like our ancestors. In these unstable, restless and hard times, the main task of every teacher is to prepare a

generation that will not run away in hard times but will bravely go to protect the motherland.

Another benefit of national games is the great contribution to our language. Reintroducing every old word into use, resisting neologisms, and waging a small struggle against language expansion is a feat comparable to this. It is the responsibility not only of linguists, but also of language protectors in various fields, to revive words that have fallen into disuse by replacing new terms with old ones.

Noting that "the future of a country that has forgotten its history is bleak", it is a scientific work equal to making a great contribution to Kazakh science by studying the works of scientists who have done any research, left memories, and expressed opinions about the Kazakh country. That's why today we need to collect, record, note the history of each field as much as possible and hand it for the future.

Main rules

It is vital and important to re-promote our national games and know the names of the scientists who entrusted them to us from the beginning of history in scientific articles at the time when the society is actively transiting into a mass digital world; all games created are in electronic devices and hand gadgets. As a result, we are facing a big transition crisis. In my opinion, it is essential to read and analyze the researches of ethnographers in the archives and to resume our national games which are written as national heritage, and present them to a younger generation in a smart and modern way.

Protecting the health, language and culture of any nation starts with raising and educating the young generation on a national base. Any of our national games disciplines a person with vigilance, agility, quick thinking, quick decision making. Moreover, games with a national education value based on fraternity, friendship and peace towards the surrounding people are interesting for not only our scientists, also for foreign ethnographers, and this is considered to be one of the most studied fields.

However, in this time of globalization and information technology when our language is copied, and games are actively played on gadgets it is crucial, and important for our society to re-develop our national games and encourage children to play in the fresh air.

It is the fastest way to make people play Kazakh national games, speak the Kazakh language, and reviving old words. That's why we should attract young generation to play national games, play with them, also supplement the series of didactic games with our original games, to contribute to spiritual revival.

Personally, I believe that due to this, many obsolete and old games have to be included in the educational program and used for focusing children's attention during the lesson, and the rules of each game, the region of origin

and the information provided by scientists and ethnographers should be available to educators and teachers.

Discussion

Consequently, given the nationalism and health benefits of today's national games. Let's use them as tools to wean children off harmful UV-emitting gadgets. If digital competence is a form of 21st century competence, we achieve many forms of competence through our games. The most important of them are language skills or language development games. Today, riddles are an indispensable tool for training children who cannot speak Russian without adding it, who think in Russian and speak Kazakh to speak fluently. A child who speaks his language fluently, in the future will become a journalist, linguist, actor, blogger, announcer, speaker, coach-trainer, etc.

Games related to horse riding make up one third of national games. It is often said that horse riding is a cure for many diseases, that a horse's skin is a powerful shield against radiation, and that a saddle soaked in horse skin can prevent snakes from biting a young person. Today, men under 30 often suffer from impotence. Sitting comfortably on a horse, pulling a horse, riding a horse, throwing an ox, learning to rope, racing, riding a horse is the only reason that not only removes various harmful diseases from the human body, but also directly affects the growth of generations.

Shooting, shooting a bow, throwing a spear, hanging tenge, etc. a lot of games, children get used to shooting and hunting. Games such as weighing coins, tiptoe, blind goat, hide-and-see, marlamkash teach children to be smart and ingenuity, while games such as altibakan, aqsuyek, and ring weight teach the art of singing.

In general, no matter what game the Kazakh people play, there are conditions. That is, the losing party pays a fine. A fine is always paid. That is why the Kazakh people's affinity to music and art begins with the demands of the game and ends with the demands of society.

It is quite possible that we can transform these games in accordance with modern requirements and turn them into didactic games played during the lesson. Sometimes difficult rules and formulas are difficult for children to remember or understand. At this point, if we explain complex scientific names by turning them into heroes or the image of a bald boy playing hide-and-see, we rework the game conditions and condition the accused group to perform a difficult task. Heart would it be easier to explain the new lesson?!

Results

We often associate the first collection of national games and their separation into several groups with the name of the famous scientist A.Divaev. Of course, A.Divaev's contribution to kazakh's ethnography is immense. We will not mention that some Russian scientists, who lived a century before him also

studied Kazakh forms of entertainment and wrote down our national culture from different regions of the Kazakh country.

For instance, in the work «History of Orenburg on the establishment of the Orenburg provinces » written in 1759 by I.I.Rychkov, extensive information about the national games of the Kazakhs in the Orinbor region is given. During 1767, P.Pallas led a Russian expedition that explored Western Siberia and the Urals, wrote a work consisting of 19 parts from the materials collected during this trip. In 1773 P.Pallas gave many cases related to national games and hunting in the section "News about Kirgiz" in his collection "Travel to various provinces of the Russian Empire".

Interesting materials from the nomadic Kazakh life were collected not only by expedition scientists, but also by Russian prisoners captured in various conflicts or exiled to Kazakh lands. They are F.S. Efremov, S. Matveev, Ya. Haverdovsky, etc. F.S. Efremov, after his release from captivity, as soon as he arrived in St. Petersburg, wrote a large-scale work from the materials he had collected from Kazakh lands, and published one chapter of that work under the name «Why is Kirgiz so rich, the air and its inhabitants».

In this chapter, the Kazakh people's daily life, hunting and hunting art, entertainment, and how their feasts are held, are skillfully described. Yefremov, who made a party not like a prisoner, but like a guest, enjoyed the hospitality of this nation, went hunting and reached his country safely, had many memories about the Kazakh people.

There, the author wrote about the life of Kazakhs in the wintering and pastures, food for long journeys, the main occupation of the nomadic people – cattle breeding and hunting. The second edition of this book published in 1794, and the third edition in 1811. Perhaps with the permission of the author or according to his words, the editor, master of historical sciences – P.Kondyrev introduced many changes and additions.[4] These additions are really essential for us today.

In the first edition of the book, some issues were not well described, in the third edition, P. Kondyrev tried to present the culture and lifestyle of the Kazakh people briefly and in a systematic way. Starting from showing the anthropological data of the Kazakhs, he described the occupation, location of nomadic people, hunting, economy, food, customs, beliefs, customary rights, weapons, and trade.

I. G. Andreev, the captain of the Russian army, was another scientist who studied the ethnography and life of the Kazakh people and wrote many works. The fifth topic of his six-chapter work « Description of the average horde of the Kirghiz-Kaisaks, with those related to this people, also adjacent to the Russian border in part of the Kalyvan and Tobolsk provinces and , serfs and others » is called «Rites ».[5] «RITES» itself consists of thirteen little themes and chapters. The third chapter is called «The birth of a baby» and shortly describing the moment of baby's birth. The fifth chapter is called the

«Wedding rites » giving the information about the rituals of betrothal, marriage, and giving a bride and concludes with information about the entertainment of young people.

Egor Arsenievich Pokrovsky (1835-1895) is the next scientist, who noticed that the nomadic people brought up children from an early age with special emphasis on physical education, noticed that the national games were of great benefit in the education of the young generation, studied in depth and wrote many works. In his work called « Physical education of children among different peoples, mainly Russia» He equates the games with the foundation of a child's life, the first working path of his future life.

Abubakir Akhmetzhanuly Divaev (1855-1932) is an scientist, who collected children's games, oral literature and lifestyle, daily life of the Kazakh people at the beginning of the 20th century. We know from Mustafa Shokai's article written for the newspaper "Kazakh" that the scientist who made a huge contribution to Kazakh culture, even though he was a Bashkir, he was highly respected by the Kazakh intellectuals of that time.

This person has long been known to all Russian scientists who are familiar with the Kazakh people in the way of science. Some of his books were published by Kazan University.

This year marks the 25th anniversary of Mr. Abubakir's service. «...It is impossible to say how much this person has benefited us in the short time of the newspaper. We are writing this to greet a friend of our people at the right place. "Mr. Abubakir does not hesitate to help poor Kazakh children studying in Tashkent," he writes. In the article, we read that the scientist was satisfied not only with science, but also with the fact that he accepted Kazakh children into his home, provided them with financial assistance, and became a consultant on educational issues. Also, Abubakir Divaev, despite his poor health, did not stop studying the heritage of the Kazakh people while sitting at home, and was impressed by his ability to translate in artistic language.

Indeed, in any work of the scientist, it can be noticeable that he pays a special attention to the Kazakh people. In his work « Kyrgyz children's games ». The names of the games were first classified, and special attention was paid to their importance in child education. He compared the types of games of the city boy and the village boy: "... when you see the toys from the factory, nothing can come to your mind except their price. These toys cannot show you what purpose and why they are made, the wishes and needs of children during the game" - he claims that those toys cannot contribute to the development of children's imagination. [8, №152] Kazakh children often make toys themselves; they sculpted figures of camels and horses from clay which are each child's unique work of art, and they value handmade toys.

In that article scientist tried not only saying talent of Kazakh children by words so he published several games and their rules as « sokyrteke » « Tuye,

tuye, tuyeler », «Uishik-Uishik », «Horde » (aksuek) «Berik Zhasyrmak », «Takya Zhasyrmak », «Domalak Agash », «Shelek ». We notice that A. Divaev classified the game into two groups and periods in his works: «balalar oiiny» and «zhas bozbalalardyn konyl koteryi». Recently, some researchers have divided the game-related works of the scientist into three groups, some even into four groups. For instance, Zhumanova M.S. In his scientific article «Uilttyk oiin ataularinyn tanimdyk meni », claims that A.A. Divaev first used the idea of scientific progress to classify Kazakh children by age: «1 zhaska deiin nereste, 1-7 deiin sebi, 7-15 deiin bozbala, 15-30 deiin zhigit» into four groups, and on the basis of that, national games concluded and were also divided into four groups. [9] In my point of view, it is better to classify the first group of physically and mentally undeveloped babies under the age of 1 in a separate category, and to classify the «sausak sanau», «besik zhiri», «tusau zhere» into children's folklore, oral literature, rather than putting them in the category of games.

The second group consists of stuffed pillows (dolls) that adapted babies to life, imitated older children, and various toys made of wood and clay or similar to them.

The third group includes games played with household items in everyday life. The fourth group covers games and national sports played by adult children. The scientist further divides this category into three groups, and they are classified as:

1. Everyday household games played at home
2. Active games played out, in nature
3. Occupation or sports games

A. Divaev not only collected his articles in a book, but also published them in newspapers. " Древние игры Киргизской молодежи", [10, №154] "Как киргизы развлекают детей" [11, 37-р] are proof of this.

Abubakir Akhmetzhanuly's passion for science, his love for researching Kazakh folklore was the main reason why the scientist's name was written in golden letters and took the first place in Kazakh literature.

At the beginning of the 20th century, one of the scientists who proposed introducing Kazakh games into the curriculum is Mikhail Mikhailovich Gunner. He divided the Kazakh national games into seven types: general games, fighting and martial games, outdoor games, winter games, resting games, horse riding games, amusement games.

In 1949, the work " short collection of Kazakh folk-national sports " was represented with additional editing by scientist M. Rakhimgulov. [13, 62-6]. In this book, types of games were divided like this: Kokpar (fighting of riders), Sais (single combat), kiz kuu (national horse riding game with the participation of a girl and a horse rider), Kumis alu — zhigitovka (collecting silver coins on a horse), Beige (local horse riding), Zhorga Zharis (pacer competition), Zhigit zhariis (riding a horse), Zhambi atu (hitting a target with

a galloping firearm), Mushe alyp kashu (fighting horseman for a prize) Attractions: Tuie zhariis (the race of camels), At omiraulastiru (push the player out of the circle), At zhegu (fast competition on preparing a horse), Tabak tartu (balanced galloping).

Alexander Efimovich Alektorov (1861-1918) was the next Russian orientalist and missionary who contributed to the study of Kazakh children's games. In his article "- The birth and upbringing of Kyrgyz children, the rules and authority of parents ", he discusses about the benefits of national games for the comprehensive development of Kazakh children, the aspects of the nomadic lifestyle that are necessary for children's health. [14, 900-970 p]

The next missionary Russian scientist who collected ethnographic data from the life of Turkic peoples (Kazakh, Uzbek, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Kalmyk, etc.) and paid special attention to national games is A. Vasiliev. In 1909, he published an article entitled "Games of Saratov's children" in the newspaper №109 "Turkistan News". The article describes the five national games of the Uzbeks of Fergana and Syrdarya: batmon-batmon (batpan-batpan), kushni bashi (bird's head), kapan skildy (trap), dupi tashar (pebbles), par aitty (flyed). [15, 109-p] M. Gavrilov in his article " Quail sport near Tashkent Sarts " shows several important types of games and customs of the Uzbek people.

As for the Kazakh poets and writers, starting with Abai, we see that all of them were sympathizers of the national game, trained runners, kept greyhounds, held eagles, and paid special attention to physical training and health. Aristocrats of Abai's time, altybakan, aqsuyek games, fox hunting clearly reflected in the poet's works. And we know from the saga "Abai zholy" that the poet entertained himself by playing the game "togizkumalak " in winter.

In the memoirs of the Russian writer Pavel Luknitsky, he perfectly described various national games, hunting, huts in the epic, and M. Auezov's desire to ride a horse. Of course, many of our scientists wrote Abay and Mukhtar's games. Some of them were limited to short articles, but Alash intellectuals often said that games have an important place in the field of education and paid special attention to children's games both during and outside of classes.

It is well known that playing any game together awakens the feelings of love, kindness and friendship in children. M. Zhumabaev sums up this moment as follows: "When a child grows up a bit and starts playing with other children, a sense of friendship is awakened in him, the child finds a friend among the children he plays with. The boy finds a friend among the children he plays with. A feeling of friendship is very useful for a child. By learning to please a friend, the child avoids selfish actions. If Magzhan considers games and friendship, child labor together, Yerzhan Sagyndykov suggests that games should be used for educational work in the classroom and outside of the

classroom, and it should be pedagogically analyzed and studied from a scientific point of view.

In his work entitled «Kazaktyn ulttyk oiindari», he splits up national games into three areas, saying: "Kazakh national games are very rich and diverse in terms of themes". [19, 74-6]

In addition to the book «Dene terbiesi men sport tarihi », the author has more than 200 scientific works, 28 books and monographs, Murakhan Tanekeev is considered a major representative of domestic sports science. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, professor, corresponding member of the World Physical Education and Sports History Committee, teacher whose works have been published in English, French, German, and Mongolian languages. For the first time in history, the development of the culture of physical education is shown as simple people and aristocratic, many of our national games before the October revolution are reprinted based on archive data, and scientific analyzes are being made. There is no doubt that his textbook «Kazakstan dene terbiesi zhonindegi tarihi» [20, 169-p] is a work beyond the reach of students. . [19, 74-p]

Along with scientist M.Taneekeev, the well-known scientist, ethnographer, doctor of historical sciences, academician Bazarbek Totenay also made a great contribution to Kazakh sports science. His book «Kazaktyn Ulttyk oiindari » [21, 144-p], is a textbook decorated with colorful pictures of about one hundred national games based on scientific references and research. This person also classified national games according to the age characteristics of children, showed the rules of the game, determined the benefits of physical education and made a scientific analysis.

The next scientist and professor is Alimkul Burkitbayev, who became a 5-time champion in boxing and became a master of sports of Kyrgyzstan. On his initiative, in 1985, a collection which is called «Sport Ulttyk oiin turleri zhene terbielik » [22, 89-p], was published. The scientist, who was a sympathizer of national sports presented national games into the daily life of children and participated in the development of horse sports and M. Balgimbayev's work Balgimbayev «Kazaktyn uiltyk sport oiiny turleri » [23, 86-p] is a work of comparative analysis of horse games.

A. Kuralbekuly and S. Akimbayuly, who studied Kazakh sports in combination with ethnopedagogy and presented their scientific and theoretical methodology, are also scientists who contribute to the development of our national sport. [24, 220-p]

Currently, E. Mukhiddinov considers the Kazakh national games in an innovative, new direction, from a socio-economic point of view, studies physical education lessons in connection with our national games, and issues works related to Kazakh wrestling. [25, 29-p]

One of the frequently used works is A.Aitpaev's «Kazaktyn ulttyk oiindarinyn teorialik negizi » where he developed a scientific and theoretical methodology

for teaching national games in primary classes of Russian-language schools and promoted folk games.

Scientist who considered the game «Togizkymalak» as one of the intellectual games of the Turkic peoples, and analyzed them in a modern, military and political way, M.Shotaev's «Tangazhail tongizmalak» greatly benefited national games and ethnopedagogy of the Kazakh people.

Conclusion

To sum up, I would say that Kazakh national games can still be an indispensable tool for comprehensive education of the young generation for centuries. National games are a part of Kazakh traditions, the golden beginning of our culture, the beginning of our spirituality, the foundation of the education of the next generation. I believe that many complex problems in today's society will begin to be solved by themselves if we unite with our national values and start educating the youth to be good through games.

Most of the scientists whose names are written above have a bold desire for yesterday's science, a desire for innovation, and even some of them did not give up science and education while in captivity, these are advanced qualities that can be shown as an example to today's generation.

Teaching students not only to play, but also to analyze any game, to inspire them to invent new games, to allow them to revive and develop games that increase language, posture and movement, adding new elements is a real indispensable skill for developing not only their critical thinking, but also their creative abilities.

Yesterday's games are today's history, national value. Today's innovation is tomorrow's legacy. We can prepare a quality generation only if we separate students from gadgets and make it a habit to discuss often what kind of legacy we leave for the next generation.

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